

Kinetics of Ion-Exchange System $[\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2]^-/\text{SO}_4^{2-}$ in Strong-Base Anion Exchanger

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The kinetics of ion-exchange between $[\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2]^-$ and SO_4^{2-} was examined under static conditions favouring particle diffusion mechanism. The calculated values of the half-time for the ion-exchange process at various temperatures were in good agreement with those obtained experimentally. That emphasized the particle diffusion mechanism. The interdiffusion coefficients were estimated and ranged between 2.69 and 4.73×10^{-7} cm^2/sec at the temperature range $20-35^\circ$. The energy of activation due to particle diffusion was 29.5 KJ/mole .

A study has been made of the kinetics of exchange between a solution of $[\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2]^-$ and a strong basic anion exchanger in the SO_4^{2-} -form. This study was carried out statically under the condition that the concerned iron-complex anion exists in decinormal sulphuric acid solution^{1,2,3}. If another species¹ of iron-complex should have existed under the present working conditions, it would have been in the form $[\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)]^+$ which plays no role in the exchange system $[\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2]^-/\text{SO}_4^{2-}$.

It was the intention of the present work to establish an easy and precise method to check up and confirm the particle diffusion mechanism.

Experimental

The Anion Exchanger

The anion exchanger Wofatit SBW (4% DVB) was the same resin used in a previous work of the same author⁴. The average particle size of the resin beads was 0.5 mm . The total capacity under static conditions was 4.385 meq/g dry resin. The resin had an apparent density of 0.7 g/cm^3 (air-dried exchanger).

The Iron Solution

A.R. grade of the salt $\text{Fe}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ which did not contain any $\text{Fe}(\text{II})$ sulphate was used. A suitable quantity of this salt was dissolved and the solution is made up to 2 L of A.R. $N/10$ H_2SO_4 . The trivalent iron in the sulphuric acid solution was easily determined quantitatively using EDTA as a titrant and salicylic acid as indicator⁵. The change of colour from dark violet to colourless or faint light yellow (depending on the amount of iron to be titrated) is very sharp. The concentration of the iron solution was 59.34 $\text{mg Fe}/100$ $\text{ml N}/10$ H_2SO_4 .

Ion-Exchange Technique

In order to restrict the anions present in the whole exchange experiments to $[\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2]^-$ and SO_4^{2-} only, iron solution and the exchanger were taken in the sulphate form. The batch-technique was used to follow the concentration change of iron during the ion-exchange process. One gram air-dried resin was used in a series of experiments. To start the experiment the resin was quickly added to the iron solution (100 ml of the standard solution) in a 150 ml Erlenmeyer-flask which was well shaken. The measurements were carried out at four various temperatures varied between 20° and 35° with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$. When the solution had been in contact with the resin for the required time it was separated by suction through a sintered glass. The amount of $[\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2]^-$ exchanged on the resin was estimated from the concentration difference between the iron solution before and after the ion-exchange process.

Results and Discussion

In the case of batch-process the mass-transfer resistance of the fluid surrounding the solid particles is negligible and the process is controlled by particle diffusion where the rate-determining step is the interdiffusion of the exchanging counter ions within the exchanger⁶.

The time dependence of the process of anion exchange between $[\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2]^-$ and SO_4^{2-} at four various temperatures is shown in Figure 1. From the Second Fick's law, Barrer⁷ developed an expression for the mathematical description of the

Fig 1. Representation of the time dependence of the process of anion-exchange between $[\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2]^-$ and SO_4^{2-} at four various temperatures.
 ○ : at 20°, □ : at 25°, × : at 30° and Δ : at 35°.

particle mechanism. This function has the following form :

$$U(t) = \frac{6}{r} \sqrt{\frac{Dt}{\pi}} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

for small values of 't' where $U(t) < 0.5$,
 $U(t) = Q_t / Q_\infty =$ Fractional attainment of equilibrium.
 (-)

Q_t = Amount exchanged per gram resin at a time t. (meq.)

Q_∞ = Amount exchanged per gram resin at equilibrium. (meq.)

r = Radius of the spherical-shaped resin particle. (0.025-cm)

t = Time of exchange. (sec.)

D = Interdiffusion coefficient. ($\text{cm}^2/\text{sec}.$)

According to equation 1 plotting $U(t)$ against \sqrt{t} gives a linear relation for small values of t and then becomes curved as can be seen in Figure 2. The slopes of the straight lines in this figure give the values of the interdiffusion coefficients of the ion-exchange system $[\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2]^-/\text{SO}_4^{2-}$ inside the resin particle (Table 1). These values of D are in good agreement with those found in the literature^{6,8,9} for some anion-exchange systems.

The activation energy for the interdiffusion of the system $[\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2]^-/\text{SO}_4^{2-}$ within the resin particle was calculated according to the relation¹⁰ :

$$D = D_0 e^{-E/RT} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

It had a value of 29.5 KJ/mole which stands in good agreement with that found in the literature^{8,11,12}, where the activation energy of particle diffusion in standard ion-exchange resins is about 25.1 to 41.84 KJ/mole.

The $t_{1/2}$ values of the interdiffusion process for the concerned ion-exchange system were calculated (Table 1) from equation 3^{13,14} :

$$t_{1/2} = 0.030 \frac{r^2}{D} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

TABLE 1—KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR THE ION-EXCHANGE SYSTEM $[\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2]^-/\text{SO}_4^{2-}$ IN WOFATIT SBW (4% DVB)

$t^\circ\text{C}$	$D \times 10^7$ (cm^2/sec)	$t_{1/2}$ (cal) (sec)	$t_{1/2}$ (obs) (sec)
20	2.69	69.6	69.6
25	3.27	57.4	57.6
30	3.97	47.2	42.0
35	4.73	39.6	34.8

From Table 1 it is clear that with increasing temperature the interdiffusion coefficient increases while the half-time of the ion-exchange process decreases.

Fig. 2. Illustration of the relation between the fractional attainment of equilibrium $U(t)$ and the square-root of 't' for the ion-exchange process between $[\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2]^-$ and SO_4^{2-} at four various temperatures.
 ○ : at 20°, □ : at 25°, × : at 30° and Δ : at 35°.

Since the capacity of the SBW resin under the present working conditions was not completely exhausted, hence the half-time of the exchange process would be equal to half the maximal amount exchanged of $[\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2]^-$ on the resin. The observed values of $t_{1/2}$ deduced from Figure 1 are found in Table 1. Comparing the calculated and observed values of $t_{1/2}$ in this Table, it is clear that they stand almost in good agreement. That emphasizes the particle diffusion mechanism as well as the great accuracy in the determination of the interdiffusion coefficients of the ion-exchange system $[\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2]^-/\text{SO}_4^{2-}$.

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